

ISic0705

I.Sicily inscription 0705

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. · D(is) · M(anibus) · ş(acrum)
2. L(ucius) · V̂ib(ius) · Sote[r]
3. vix(it) · ann(is) · XLI[---]
4. V̂ib(ia) Lecata vix(it)
5. ann(is) XXXVI L(ucius) V̂ib(ius)
6. Niceros · f(ecit) filius

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Lucius Vibius Soter lived for 41(?) years, Vibia Lecata lived for 36 years, Lucius Vibius Niceros, their son, built this

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175767

EDR 138811
EDCS 6100270

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0341h

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 142

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 171 no.38 fig.42

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